
Pest management and control

DISEASES

Bacterial blight found in Africa

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Bacterial blight (BB) of rice, caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae*, is endemic to Asia and is the most important and damaging bacterial disease of rice. In 1973, BB was reported in northern tropical Australia — the first report from outside Asia. In 1975, it was discovered on and around some rice experiment stations in Colombia and Panama. Although no reports of BB from Africa or Malagasy had been confirmed, there have been

private unconfirmed reports of symptoms resembling those of BB in earlier Taiwanese rice projects in several West African countries on the variety TN1, which was introduced in the 1960s. The senior author searched for the disease in many African countries during the last 4 years but did not detect its presence, even in older rice-growing areas.

In the 1978 growing season, symptoms resembling BB were noted at a rice experiment station at Kogoni, Mali. The authors visited the station in mid-November, at the end of the growing season, and found typical BB symptoms in one block of the variety Gambiaka kokum. Even kresek was found in some plants. Gambiaka kokum is a local tall indica that was grown in large blocks, along with other varieties, for seed distribution. □

Udbatta disease (*Ephelis oryzae*) was observed only in Sarguja district, Bilaspur division, on a local variety in 1969 kharif, and later at Dhamatari block, Raipur district, in 1973 kharif.

Sogatella furcifera is an important rice insect pest in Raipur and Bilaspur regions. About 5% of its adults were found dead with expanded wings on rice plants. Isolations from the dead insects yielded a fungus identified as *Fusarium* sp. Pathogenicity was proved. This may be the first record of this fungus on *S. furcifera* in India. □

Potential of weeds to spread rice tungro in West Bengal, India

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Many graminaceous and cyperaceous weeds can act as symptomless carriers of rice tungro virus disease. An experiment was conducted to determine the potential of weeds to spread tungro in the plant virus experimental rice field at Kalyani, where tungro occurs throughout the year. Virus incidence was surveyed in 1976–77 and 1977–78. The predominant cyperaceous and graminaceous weeds (see table) were brought to the glasshouse and tested for the presence of tungro by indexing the disease incidence on Taichung Native 1 (TN1) seedlings. Virus-free weeds were then inoculated with viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* and tested for virus at 1-month intervals. The percentage of transmission to TN1 seedlings was recorded weekly. Only *Echinochloa colonum* and *Paspalum notatum* transmitted the virus. *E. colonum* infected 16% of the plants, *P. notatum* 20%.

To study the actual potential of the infected weeds to transmit the virus in the field, *E. colonum* plants were grown in pots and inoculated with tungro in

Observations on rice diseases and insects in Madhya Pradesh, India

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Certain observations have been made on rice diseases at Raipur, India.

Rice blast (*Pyricularia oryzae*) is the most important disease in Raipur and Bilaspur divisions, the main rice-growing areas of M.P. Neck blast is usually more important and damaging than leaf blast.

Bacterial blight (*Xanthomonas oryzae*) is the next most important disease of cultivated rice. It was first noticed in the area in 1965. In 1970 kharif, blight was observed on *Oryza rufipogon*, a wild rice growing in tanks at Raipur. Brown spot (*Helminthosporium oryzae*), still a minor disease in the area, was also seen on *Oryza rufipogon*.

Bacterial leaf streak (*Xanthomonas translucens* f. sp. *oryzicola*) was first

noticed on a few lines of the cross 34/32 at the rice research farm in 1967. It occurred in epidemic form on IR8 in 1968 kharif. It has also been seen on another wild rice, *Oryza perennis*.

Sheath blight (*Corticium sasakii*) is minor but spreading in the area. During varietal screening, its basidial state was observed in densely growing paddy that was affected by sheath blight.

Stack burn (*Trichoconis padwickii*) is a minor disease, observed only on leaves of semidwarf varieties. In 1972 kharif the following varieties grown in disease screening trials were affected with traces of stack burn while other varieties were free: BCp sp. 1, CR120-181, CR120-182, C24550 (GEB/IR8), C1244(RDR7/TN1), MR89, MR106 (TN1/TKM6), OR10-257 (T90/IR8), R1912 (CO29/IR8), R1922 (CO29/IR8), RP4-12 (T90/IR8), RP4-12 (T90/IR8), RP20-9 (GEB24/Sigadis//IR8), RP175-1, Saturn 587-4 (short culm), Sambalpur E. No. 166, W1251, and No. 6948.0

Composition of graminaceous and cyperaceous weed flora during a 2-year period at the plant virus experimental field, Kalyani, West Bengal, India.

Weed	Av no./m ²		Relative occurrence (%)	
	1976-77	1977-78	1976-77	1977-78
<i>Echinochloa colonum</i> (Graminae)	182	300	53.8	43.8
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> (Cyperaceae)	55	174	16.2	25.4
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (Graminae)	71	122	21.1	17.8
<i>Paspalum notatum</i> (Graminae)	30	58	8.8	8.5

kharif. The pots were used as virus sources in the field 35 to 40 days after inoculation. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of TN1, Jaya, and Ratna were transplanted in replicated 1-m² plots prepared in random block design. One pot of inoculated *E. colonum* was placed

at the center of each plot. Each plot was then covered with nylon netting on wooden frames. Freshly emerged leafhoppers were released into each covered plot. The plants in each plot were observed until the booting stage. Ratna plants had 1.57% infection; Jaya,

6.4%; and TN1, 7.5%.

From this experiment it is apparent that the predominant graminaceous and cyperaceous weeds at the Kalyani virus experimental field do not contain any virus in natural conditions.

Weeds collected at Kalyani and other locations were inoculated with the virus. Only *E. colonum* and *P. notatum* were able to maintain the virus for 3 months.

In the field study with the inoculated *E. colonum* as the source plant, the virus was transmitted to all three test varieties (Ratna, Jaya, and TN1). Thus it is apparent that infected weeds such as *E. colonum* can act as the tungro virus source in the field. But no virus was detected in the weeds in natural conditions. Therefore, weeds may not play an important role in the field transmission of tungro. □

Occurrence of *Phaeotrichoconis crotalariae* on rice in Karnataka, India

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Many prerelease and released paddy cultures suffered from grain discoloration in 1977 kharif and 1978 summer in experimental plots at the Regional Research Station, VC Farm, Mandya, Karnataka. Derivatives of Basumathi and Sabarmati were particularly affected. When the discolored kernels were surface sterilized and incubated in moist chambers at room temperature (25-27°C), abundant spores of *Phaeotrichoconis crotalariae*, as well as the commonly known fungi involved in discoloration, were encountered. The fungus was easily isolated by the single-spore technique and pure-cultured on potato-dextrose agar. In the initial stages, the mycelial growth was whitish, but at maturity became dark grey. Conidia were produced after 4 days; sclerotia developed after 8 to 10 days. Descriptions of the fungus are similar to those provided by Subramanyam in 1956 and Vaidehi in 1971. Vaidehi had

isolated this fungus from TN1 rice kernels collected in 1967 in Andhra Pradesh, but the same fungus now occurs regularly and abundantly on many rice

varieties in Karnataka. This is the only information reported on its widespread occurrence on different rice varieties in Karnataka.

A rice disease observed by the late Bill Golden in Nepal

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After reading the article "Symptoms resembling those of rice dwarf disease in the Kathmandu Valley, Nepal" in the

IRRN 3(6):13-14, 1978, I found a color slide that was given to me by the late William (Bill) G. Golden, Jr., former IRRI rice production specialist and formerly with IRRI outreach programs in Sri Lanka and Bangladesh. The slide, taken by Bill in Kathmandu, Nepal, on 3 October 1966, shows A. N. Bhattarai

A photograph from a color slide taken by the late William G. Golden, Jr., in Kathmandu, Nepal, in 1966 showing A. N. Bhattarai holding a rice hill with symptoms similar to those of rice dwarf disease described in Japan.